

Communication Plan for the European project Soil O-Live

**(The soil biodiversity and functionality of
Mediterranean olive groves: a holistic analysis of the
influence of land management on olive oil quality
and safety)**

	PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN					
	DELIVERABLE					
	Title	FARMS LOCATION				
	D.7.15		Publication date	11/28/2023	Version	1
Prepared by	A.J.M.A.	Approved by	A.J.M.A.	Page	1 of 16	

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1.-Introduction

This document aims to serve as a guide for the strategy and communication actions of the Soil O-Live European project. Its main objective is to spread awareness about the project and encourage olive growers and other key stakeholders to participate. Additionally, it seeks to improve the practices and land use of the Mediterranean olive groves. We will identify the target audiences, determine the most effective communication channels, and develop other relevant actions to achieve these goals.

It's important to note that since this is a European project, we need to ensure maximum visibility for the European Union, which is the source of these funds and promotes the dissemination of good practices, as in the case of Soil O-Live. The plan will be based on being efficient, cost-effective, concrete, and realistic. The contents of this plan will be written in Spanish and English, while social media posts will be in Spanish, English, and occasionally Italian, Portuguese, and Greek.

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2.-Target audience:

The main targets of Soil O-live are:

- Scientific community (research peers)
- Farmers associations
- Non associated farmers
- Policymakers at regional, national, and European scales.
- Olive mills and cooperatives (i.e., industry)
- General public, including consumers

3.-Key messages to be transmitted:

Data from the European Union Soil Observatory (EUSO) indicates that 60-70% of both agricultural and non-agricultural soils in Europe are degraded and have functional limitations. Olive groves in the Mediterranean Region have been subjected to intensive agriculture for over fifty years, leading to a significant decline in environmental conditions. This has resulted in biodiversity loss, degradation, and a general decline in functionality, which may have already affected the quality of olive oil. The main goals of the project are thus the main messages to be transmitted to the project's target as follows:

- Soil O-live conducts a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental conditions of olive grove soils on a large scale, focusing on the most crucial olive production regions in the**

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Mediterranean area. This assessment establishes the correlation between the quality of olive groves and olive oil and soil conditions.

-Particular messages:

-The objective of the study is to analyze the impact of pollution, mainly by pesticides and copper, and land degradation on olive soils. The study will focus on the multi-biodiversity and ecological function at different levels and scales.

-The study will investigate the relationship of soil health status with the quality and safety of olive oil.

- The research will implement effective soil amendments and ecological restoration practices that promote improvements in biodiversity and soil functionality in permanent Mediterranean olive groves in their native range. ***The expected outcome is to improve olive oil quality and safety.***

- Finally, the study aims to define rigorous ecological thresholds that will allow the implementation of clear rules and regulations. This will help design a novel certification for healthy soils in European olive groves.

- European soil health law (Soil health-protecting, sustainably managing and restoring EU soils).

- Soil restoration for agricultural lands across the Mediterranean.

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Other tags:

- Horizon Europe Project
- Soil Mission Project
- Project financed by the European Union.
- Project coordinated by the University of Jaén.
- Project coordinated by the University of Jaén through the University Institute for Research in Olive Oil and Olive Oils.
- European project with 17 partners, including companies and institutions.

4.-Communication channels:

In order to effectively reach our intended audience, we plan to utilize a diverse range of communication channels, both online (such as websites, blogs, social media, and email) and offline (like television, radio, press, specialized events, etc.). It is essential to communicate with the media as it has the potential to reach a large audience and help spread information about our European project, which can ultimately lead to positive opinions towards it. To achieve this, we intend to maintain an active relationship with journalists and the media. For this purpose, Soil O-live is assisted by a specialized press company (Hermes Communication Press).

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For the European Soil O-Live project, we have identified the following channels to begin with:

4.1. Website / Corporate Blog

The project will have a tool that hosts important information and serves as a source for social media updates. The communication section (blog), containing press releases and photographs, will be particularly important. If applicable, an Image Gallery will be included. This section will also be updated with other types of content, such as interviews and reports.

-Profiles of the partners that make up the project and the people behind each company and institution related to Soil O-Live.

-Specific texts for the media.

-Presentation graphics of every one of the partners.

-Compilation of some of the most relevant news published by the media about the project.

-Activities, news, and participation in events of the project members.

- Access to published papers and link to public data

*The blog is an important communication channel to attract users and reach our target audience through relevant content in social networks and improved web positioning.

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4.2. Social Networks

The following is a breakdown of the target audiences and content focus for each social media platform in the project's communication plan:

- Facebook: The content on this platform is aimed at farmers, the general public, and consumers between the ages of 40 and 75.

- Twitter (X): Agricultural associations, media, agriculture, and olive oil professionals, legislators, and policymakers, among others, are the target audience for the content on Twitter.

- Instagram: The content on this platform is more transversal, with an aim to reach all target audiences as outlined in the communication plan. The focus of the content is on informative and awareness-raising messages about good practices in the care of the olive grove and the environment in general.

- LinkedIn This platform is the project's social network of reference, with more technical content aimed mainly at researchers, professionals in the olive sector, and media specialized in agriculture and the environment.

-YouTube®: This channel will host the videos that will be elaborated in the framework of this communication plan, as well as other videos that may be relevant for the members of the project consortium and other related European projects, interviews and reports.

- Whatshap®: Allows direct communication with the farmers and is responsible of the cooperatives linked to the project.

-Telegram®: it allows a **larger audiences reach**, because Telegram allows a channel to have unlimited members, hence it can reach a wide audience. This makes it beneficial for businesses or groups that want to communicate to a large number of people at once. **Message Dissemination:** In a Telegram channel, only admins can send messages which are then received by all the members. This ensures one-way

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communication where vital information can be disseminated without interruptions or unnecessary chatter.

*The social network TikTok could be considered for inclusion in this category at a later stage.

Hermes Comunicación and Soil O-live communication team plans to update social networks 2-3 times a week, with varying rates per platform to adapt to their characteristics.

About the hashtags to use:

#SoilOlive #OliveOil #Soil #OliveOil #Europe #EuropeanFunds
 #Olives #Soil #Olive #Environment #Ecology
 #EuropeanCommission #SoilMission #HorizonEurope #UJA.

4.3. Media

We plan to work closely with the project's dissemination team and the Press Office of the coordinator, the University of Jaén. Our goal is to gather relevant information and create press releases that highlight the project's objectives. The press releases will be distributed among various media outlets, including regional, national, international, and specialized media covering the topics of Olive Oil, Agriculture, Economy, Environment, and Sustainability.

Moreover, we will handle all necessary arrangements with journalists and media managers to secure radio and television interviews and news and reports in national and specialized media. Tools to be used:

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-Press releases, memorandums, photographs. Sending one or two press releases per month.

The press releases will be available on the project's website simultaneously with their distribution to the media. These releases will contain image galleries, enabling journalists and media personnel to download the images that are most relevant to them. Additionally, the press releases will be promptly shared on social media platforms, with links to the project's website. This will drive traffic to the website, allowing people to access comprehensive information about the project.

-Press conferences for relevant findings and milestones.

*The opportunity and convenience of the same, for example, at the time of presenting the results of the research.

*The places where it is developed must have:

-Corporate image

-Light and sound (favoring a good image).

5. Direct actions

1) **Publications in scientific journals (target research peers):**

our project involves soil ecology environmental research. To ensure that our findings reach a wider audience, we plan to publish the most relevant results in top multidisciplinary journals such as Nature, Nature Communications, Nature Sustainability, Nature Microbiology, Nature Chemistry, npj Biodiversity, npj

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Biofilms and Microbiomes, Science, Science Advances, and PNAS. Paper production will begin after the diagnostic stage is completed, which is expected to be after month 18. We will also make use of specialized portals to publish pre-prints and opt for open access mode.

2) ***Dissemination of scientific results in specialized meetings, symposiums, workshops and seminars (target: research peers)***. We will select annually at least three international meetings, symposiums, workshops and/or seminars to disseminate our results to the scientific community. Some examples of candidate forums are the World Congress of Soil Science (joint meeting of the British Society of Soil Science and the International Union of Soil Science), Eurosoil meeting (European Confederation of Soil Science Societies), Global Symposium on Soil Biodiversity (FAO, UN), International Symposium on Agroecology (FAO, UN), Global Symposium on Soil Erosion (FAO, UN), Agroecology Europe Forum (European Association for Agroecology), World Conference on Ecological Restoration (Society for Ecological Restoration), Sibecol, and, especially the Soil Mission Week.

3) ***Holding of the Workshop on sustainability and biodiversity in Olive Groves (target: peers, stakeholders, policymakers, farmer associations)***, taking advantage of consortium experience in the coordination and participation on several European projects related to sustainability on olive groves, at month 24, we plan to promote, coordinate and develop the first

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joint sustainability workshop of olive groves where we will share main findings of each project looking for general patterns and solutions to environmental challenges that olive growing currently present in the Mediterranean region. This will also be held in collaboration with the UC Davis Olive Center.

4) ***Communication of project activities and advances in specialized olive growing and olive oil production meetings, symposiums, workshops, and seminars (target: stakeholders, farmer associations, policymakers).*** We will select the most important international forum annually to explain the main goals and motivations of the Soil O-live project and relevant advances. Candidate forums are Expoliva (International Fair of Olive Oil), World Olive Oil Exhibition, the Kalamata olive and olive oil festival-Greece etc.

6) ***Communication of project activities and advances of Soil O-live designed specifically for farmers and producers (cooperatives and mills) (target: farmers and producers).*** Implementing sustainable practices in olive groves is crucial for the environment and the quality of the final product. Soil O-live project aims to promote this cause among farmers, and the involvement of Deoleo Global is essential to achieve its objectives. By coordinating the workshops, Deoleo Global can directly influence farmers to adopt environmental and quality standards that meet the requirements of olive oil trade companies. These standards are essential to meet the expectations of consumers. To maximize the impact of the

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project, Deoleo Global will also conduct an extensive press media campaign to raise public awareness of Soil O-live activities.

7) Seminars Master Academic Programs. (Target: alumni and professionals) Academic members of the Soil O-live consortium will impart seminars in specialized Agroecology, Agronomy, Restoration and/or Olive Growing and Olive Oil Master Programs. For example, in Spain, candidate Master's Programs are:

University Master's degree in Restoration Ecology (University of Jaén).

Master's Degree in Oliviculture and Elaiotechnique (University of Córdoba, Spain), Master's degree on Biotechnology (University of Granada), in Greece the Sustainable Agriculture International Master program of the Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Chania (CIHEAM_MAICH), Crete, involving students from Mediterranean countries

8) Contribution to Standardization (target: Standardization Technical Committees). Soil O-live will build upon existing standards for the analyses to be carried out and the new processes and systems to be developed ensuring compatibility with what is expressed through standards. Furthermore, Soil O-live will be linked with ongoing standardization work like, e.g., in ISO/TC 134 "Fertilizers and soil conditioners", ISO/TC 190 "Soil quality", CEN/TC 223 "Soil improvers and growing media" or CEN/TC 455 "Plant Biostimulants". This will support the dissemination of the project, its activities and results. In addition,

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the feedback from the stakeholders organized in standardization will improve Soil-Olive's contribution to standardization when forwarding inputs from Soil O-live's findings and results to the above-mentioned technical committees for improving existing standards or to initiate the development of new ones. UNE, representing CENCENELEC will lead these activities

Other complementary activities:

- During the Expoliva International Fair, visitors can obtain informative material about extra virgin olive oil and related products. They can also visit the stands of cooperatives and olive oil mills to learn more about their products.
- In addition, there will be opportunities for meetings and potential collaboration agreements with designations of origin, IGP, Agro-Alimentary Cooperatives, Asaja, COAG, irrigation communities, olive oil mills and cooperatives.
- The following actions will be taken to promote the Soil O-Live project:
 - Explanatory videos about the project, highlighting its financing by European funds, will be disseminated in all events where Soil O-Live is present.
 - Annual International Olive Oil Contest for olive oil quality. Olive oils from Soil O-live farms will be evaluated for quality with the support of the International Olive Council.

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- The project will commemorate the following world days - Environment Day (June 5), World Agriculture Day (September 9), and World Olive Tree Day (November 26) - with graphics, videos, press releases, and activities involving educational centers, associations, the scientific community, etc.

- Participation in the Science Week and Researchers' Night of the participating universities will be ensured.

-Visits to farms within the framework of the project:

6.-Periodic evaluation of results

It is important to evaluate the effectiveness of the communication plan annually to determine if desired results are being achieved. This will allow for adjustments to be made to actions that are not meeting expectations and reinforcement of those that are successful. The evaluation can be done by assessing the quality and quantity of media appearances, analyzing social media metrics such as number of followers, interaction, follower demographics, and follower assessment of the project, and evaluating content that has better and worse acceptance. It is also important to analyze the image projected and public opinion generated by Soil O-Live.

7.-Internal communication

It's crucial to foster a sense of belonging in project members, making them feel like ambassadors of its principles and objectives. The Coordinator along with the responsible of the WP7 package (communication), will coordinate all the

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communication and dissemination activities. In addition, they will evaluate the impact of the communication and dissemination program.